

ANTİBAKTERİYEL KAĞIT ÜRETİMİ

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ÖZET

Bu çalışmada, yüksek antibakteriyel özelliği olan sarımsak yağı ve gümüş nitrat ile antibakteriyel kağıt üretimi amaçlanmıştır. Sarımsak yağı ve gümüş nitratin antibakteriyel etkisini belirlemek için altı farklı bakteri (*Klebsiella oxyfoca*, *Enterobacter amnigenus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus hemolyticus*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Cornibacterium xerosis* ve *Bacillus cereus*) ve iki farklı mantar (*Rhodotorula rubra* ve *Kluyveromyces marxianus*) türü kullanılmıştır. 70 (gr/m²) gramajında üretilen kağıtlara antibakteriyel özellikte olan sarımsak yağı ve gümüş nitrat belirli oranlarda emdirilmiştir.

Elde edilen sonuçlara göre, gümüş nitrat bütün bakteriler üzerinde etkili olmazken sarımsak yağı hepsinde etkili olmuştur. Her iki madde de mantarlar üzerinde pozitif bir etki göstermiştir. Sarımsak yağı *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* bakterisi türünde ve *Rhodotorula rubra* mantar türünde daha etkili olurken gümüş nitrat ise *Bacillus cereus* bakterisi türünde ve *Kluyveromyces marxianus* mantar türünde daha etkili olmuştur. Üretimi yapılan antibakteriyel kağıtlar, ilk yardım üniteleri, klinikler, cerrahi, yeni doğan üniteleri, diş üniteleri vb. yerlerde enfeksiyon yayılımını önlemek için kullanılabilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Antibakteriyel kağıt, gümüş nitrat, sarımsak yağı

ANTIBACTERIAL PAPER PRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study was to produce antibacterial paper used silver nitrate (AgNO₃) and garlic oil (*Allium sativum*) which have antibacterial properties. Six different bacteria (*Klebsiella oxyfoca*, *Enterobacter amnigenus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus hemolyticus*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Cornibacterium xerosis* and *Bacillus cereus*) and two different fungi (*Rhodotorula rubra* and *Kluyveromyces marxianus*) were used in this study in order to determine antibacterial effects of garlic oil and silver nitrate. Garlic oil and silver nitrate were impregnated to the papers produced with grammages of 70 (gr/m²) in certain rates.

The results show that while silver nitrate is not effective on all bacteria, garlic oil has been effective and they showed a positive effect on fungi. Silver nitrate was more effective on *Bacillus cereus* and *Kluyveromyces marxianus* while garlic oil was more effective on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Rhodotorula rubra*. The produced antibacterial papers can be used in clinics, neonatal units, dental units, first aid units, surgeon etc. in order to prevent infectious diseases.

Keywords: Antibacterial paper, silver nitrate, garlic oil.

Introduction

Antiseptics are antimicrobial substances that are applied to living tissue/skin to reduce the possibility of infection, sepsis, or putrefaction. Antiseptics are generally distinguished from antibiotics by the latter's ability to be transported through the lymphatic system to destroy bacteria within the body, and from disinfectants, which destroy microorganisms found on non-living objects (Gerald and Denver, 1999). Antibacterials antiseptic that have proven ability to act against bacteria and its infections and may either kill or inhibit the growth of bacteria.

Mankind lives continuously with microorganisms in their active activities. In daily life napkins are used for cleaning purposes in homes, restaurants, dining halls and washbasins. It is extremely important that these napkins should be antimicrobial in terms of human health. Also, materials such as paper towels, cleaning papers, sterilized clothes, and patient scrubs used in hospitals, operating rooms, and dental clinics should be antibacterial. According to the legal regulations, these materials must be antibacterial by law (Gunaydin, 2010).

Paper consumption in the world is steadily increasing despite the developments in technology. It is a versatile material that has a lot of usage area. Although it is widely used for printing or printing purposes, it has found many uses in cleaning and packaging industries and construction sectors. In particular, the papers used in the health and cleaning sectors are required to be hygienic in order to prevent infections and diseases.

Some investigations have shown that chemical compounds of garlic (Fig. 1) have antimicrobial activity against various microorganisms (Weber et al., 1992; Hanafy et al., 1994; Ahsan and Islam, 1996; Yoshida et al., 1998). For instance, Alliin and Allicin formed by the enzymatic reaction of alliin have a lethal effect on microorganisms. These compounds are on duty in the inhibition of the growth of many bacteria and fungi. Another essential oil, Ajoene, is fungicidal and has an inhibitory effect on reproduction (Block, 1985; Block; 2010). During The World War I, British army used garlic in order to medically treat contaminations of injured soldiers. They put a mixture of fresh garlic juice with water straight into the wound: medical effect was excellent. During The World War II, Russian Soviet doctors applied the same medication. In World War II garlic was called 'Russian Penicillin' because, after running out of antibiotics, the soviet government turned to these ancient treatments for its soldiers (Baruchin et al., 2001).

Figure 4. Garlic grown in Taşköprü

The antimicrobial properties of silver have been known for centuries in the world. Silver can be administered to cells in a various number of ways. Silver salts such as silver nitrate (AgNO_3) are effective at providing a large quantity of silver ions all at once. For example, AgNO_3 is used

to treat burns (Russell and Chopra, 1990) and to prevent eye infections (Slawson et al., 1992). Because silver binds to thiol groups, it has been proposed that although one of the antimicrobial mechanisms of Ag⁺ is binding to sulfur-containing compounds, thiol-containing compounds such as proteins with cysteine residues can also serve to absorb the silver ions and neutralize their antibacterial activity by preventing the silver ions from attacking DNA (Liau et al., 1997).

Especially in the health sector, special antimicrobial papers are widely used. These papers are used in first aid unit, surgeon, clinic, newborn child unit, dental unit etc. The aim of this study is to produce antimicrobial papers with using garlic oil and silver nitrate in order to prevent infection and infectious diseases.

Material and Methods

Materials

The garlic oil (odor-free) used in the study was obtained from a commercial herbalist. Silver nitrate (AgNO₃) was supplied from Kahramanmaraş Sutcu Imam University (KSU). The bacteria (*Klebsiella oxytoca*, *Enterobacter amnigenus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus hemolyticus*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Cornibacterium xerosis*, *Bacillus cereus*) and fungi (*Rhodotorula rubra*, *Kluyveromyces marxianus*) were taken from KSU, Biology Department, and Microbiology Laboratory. Bleached hardwood pulps were used for paper production.

Antimicrobial Paper Production

The pulps were adjusted to 0.5% concentration by the addition of tap water. Handsheets per tested sequence with grammages of 70 g·m⁻² were prepared using a Rapid-Kothen sheet former according to ISO 5269/2. Square papers with an edge length of 6 cm were obtained from these papers. 3% garlic oil and AgNO₃ solutions were prepared and impregnated to the papers. Impregnated papers were dried at room temperature and conditioned at 23±1 °C and 65% relative humidity in conditioning room accordance with TAPPI T 402 om-88 standard. The papers were sized to be 10 and 14 mm in diameter in order to determine inhibition zones.

Activation of stock cultures was carried out in Nutrient Broth Medium. Mueller-Hinton-Agar Medium was used to determine antibiotic effects of garlic oil and AgNO₃. 25 ml of medium was placed into the sterilized tubes. These tubes were inoculated with the mentioned bacteria and fungi species. Tubes were incubated for 24 hours in tube 32°C for the development of bacteria and fungi. 2 µl of bacteria and fungi were inoculated with micropipette onto the Mueller-Hinton-Agar Medium sterilized in Erlenmeyer flasks and shaken thoroughly, then dispersed in sterilized petri dishes and homogeneously distributed in the petri dish. The papers impregnated with garlic oil and AgNO₃ were placed on the solid agar by slightly pressing. Prepared petri dishes were incubated for 24 hours at 32 °C. Then, the inhibition zones formed on the mediums were evaluated in millimeter.

Results and Discussion

The results of the antibacterial assessment of paper incorporated with garlic oil and AgNO₃ against six selected bacteria and two selected fungi is presented in Table 1.

The results of the antimicrobial activity of the garlic oil and AgNO₃ were given in Tables 1 and 2. Inhibition zones formed on 10 mm and 14 mm diameter papers were shown in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. A sample inhibition zone image of control (C), garlic oil (G), and AgNO₃ (S) against *Kluyveromyces marxianus* (F-2) was illustrated in Fig. 2.

Figure 5. Inhibition zones of control (C), garlic oil (G), and AgNO₃ (S) formed on 14 mm diameter paper against *Kluyveromyces marxianaas*

Table 5. The inhibition zones (mm) of bacteria and fungi formed on 10 mm diameter papers impregnated with garlic oil and AgNO₃

Bacteria and Fungi Types	Inhibition Zones (mm)		
	Control	AgNO ₃	Garlic Oil
<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i> (B-1)	0	12	15
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (B-2)	0	12	20
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> (B-3)	0	10	19
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (B-4)	0	12	23
<i>Cornebacterium xerosis</i> (B-5)	0	8	15
<i>Bacillus cereus</i> (B-6)	0	23	20
<i>Rhodotorula rubra</i> (F-1)	0	16	23
<i>Kluyveromyces marxianaas</i> (F-2)	0	18	17

*Control refers to untreated papers.

As shown in Table 1, it was determined that garlic oil and AgNO₃ used in this study showed different effects on bacteria and fungi. AgNO₃ was most effective on the B-6 and inhibition zone was found to be 23 mm. The same bacteria formed 20 mm inhibition zone on paper impregnated with garlic oil. AgNO₃ have no effect on B-5, but garlic oil affected the same bacteria. Gopalakrishnan et al. (2015), Silambarasan and Abraham (2012) reported that AgNO₃ is a highly effective antibiotic against *B. cereus*. AgNO₃ showed almost the same effect on the fungi but not as much as the bacteria. As illustrated in Fig. 3A, garlic oil was more effective on the bacteria and fungi compared to AgNO₃.

Figure 6. Effects of garlic oil and AgNO₃ on the inhibition zones (mm) of bacteria and fungi formed on 10 mm (A) and 14 mm (B) diameter papers

Inhibition zones formed on 14 mm diameter papers were shown in Table 2. When the table was examined, garlic oil was generally effective on all bacteria and fungi and showed the highest effect on B-4 (31 mm) and F-1 (30 mm). In many studies on garlic oil, it has been reported that garlic oil is an important antibiotic against bacteria and fungi (Rees et al., 1993; Lawson, 1996; Lawson, 1998; O'Gara et al., 2000; Ross et al., 2001; Du et al., 2009; Dobre et al., 2011).

Table 6. The inhibition zones (mm) of bacteria and fungi formed on 14 mm diameter papers impregnated with garlic oil and AgNO₃

BacteriaandFungiTypes	InhibitionZones (mm)		
	Control	AgNO ₃	GarlicOil
<i>Klebsiellaoxycola</i> (B-1)	0	15	26
<i>Escherichacoli</i> (B-2)	0	24	24
<i>AcinetobacterBaumannii</i> (B-3)	0	25	21
<i>Pseudomonasaeruginosa</i> (B-4)	0	18	31
<i>Cornebacteriumxerosis</i> (B-5)	0	20	25
<i>Bacilluscereus</i> (B-6)	0	23	21
<i>Rhodotorulanubra</i> (F-1)	0	16	30
<i>Kluyveromycesmarxianaas</i> (F-2)	0	21	21

*Control refers to untreated papers.

According to Table 2, compared to garlic oil and AgNO₃, garlic oil is more effective against bacteria and fungi. B-3 and F-2 were the most affected bacteria and fungi from AgNO₃ and the inhibition zones formed on 14 mm paper were 25 mm and 21 mm, respectively. Garlic oil is more effective against B-4 and F-1. Inhibition zones of these bacteria and fungus was found as 31 mm and 21 mm, respectively (Fig. 3B).

It has been reported that garlic oil is effective against many bacterial agents such as *Helicobacter pylori*, *E. coli*, *Lactobacillus casei* as an antibacterial agent. It is estimated that the effects is caused by Allicin, which contains garlic (Hanafy et al., 1994; Yoshida et al., 1998). The antimicrobial activity of garlic oil against *H. pylori* and *Aspergillus* species has been also reported (Pai and Platt, 1995; O’Gara et al, 2000). The results of our present study show the antimicrobial activity of garlic oil against six other medically important pathogens. Since about 50% of garlic oil consisted of these four diallylsulphides (Lawson et al., 1991) and these sulphides also possessed antibacterial activities.

Liu et al., (2014) reported that *A. baumannii* was susceptible toamikacin which an antibiotic used for a number of bacterial infections, in the presence ofsilver. In this study, AgNO₃is most effective on *A. baumannii* bacteria on 14 mm diameter papers.The effect of silver ions on microorganisms has not been fully understood. However, various researches have revealed that the bacteria, fungi or virus cells attacked by silver ions have disrupted the respiratory system.

Conclusion

The findings of the current study unveiled powerful and broad spectrum antimicrobial activity of garlic oil and AgNO₃ against a large number of human and animal pathogenic bacteria and fungi. Further investigations on the active antimicrobial components in garlic oil and AgNO₃ are required to provide the pharmaceutical companies with cheap and effective antimicrobial agent.

Silver nitrate was more effective on *Bacillus cereus* and *Kluyveromycesmarxianus* while garlic oil was more effective on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*and *Rhodotorularubra*. The produced antibacterial papers can be used in clinics, neonatal unit, dental unit, first aid unit, surgeon etc. in order to prevent infectious diseases.

One the important requirement for health and cleaning sectors is antimicrobial paper. Paper has great potential to be made a desired structural form. This study suggests that it is possible to produce antibacterial paper capable of killing and catching pathogenic microorganisms.

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